

**THE IMPORTANCE OF CREATING AGROPHYTOCENOSES IN
IMPROVING THE ECOLOGICAL CONDITION OF PASTURES****Alimkulova R.A.,****Sodiqova P.M.,****Kushakova F.U.**

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Abstract: In this paper livestock breeding and prospects of this development are discussed. Scientific deductions regarding methods of raising fertility in the pasture, improving and optimizing ecological wellbeing of the crops are also included. Suggestion concerning the production of synthetic. By analyzing are as well included. Suggestion concerning the production of synthetic. By analyzing are as well included.

Key words: plants, pasture, cattle – raising, desertification.

Introduction. The adoption of the law of the Republic of 2017 – 2021 on the development of the economy in the state program for the development of the economy “development strategy” for 2021 – 2026, as well as the law “on pastures” on April 2, 2019, means how urgent this issue is that it is aimed at improving the ecological state of pastures. This requires the implementation of a set of measures aimed at improving the ecological condition of pastures, that is, conducting fundamental, applied, innovative scientific research in the field of scientific study of this area.

Main part. One of the important issues is the classification of the 32 million hectares of pastures available in the republic on the basis of scientific study of their ecological condition and monitoring, while only 17.8 million hectares of common pastures are used for the development of pasture livestock. Given that most of the pastures have been eroded to varying degrees, this amount can be further reduced. Over the next 10-15 years, 2 million hectares of pastures were completely eroded and could no longer be used (Makhmudov 2005).

Due to the further development of pastoral cattle breeding in our republic, it is possible to ensure food security, achieve development in the regions of karakul breeding, camel breeding, horse breeding, which are the main branches of animal husbandry, increase the production of products from them (leather, meat, milk). Thus, it is possible to meet the demand of the population for food and ensure their employment at work. In the future, through scientific study of the ecological state of pastures, it is advisable to carry out phytomeliorative measures aimed at increasing the species and quantitative number of plants, ensuring biodiversity, it is possible to increase the yield of pastures by 3-5 times, further enriching them with nutrients.

To do this, it is advisable to use the conclusions and innovations of the scientific experiment of a number of research institutes. Increasing the productivity of pastures the creation of artificial pastures gives a good result the creation of new artificial pastures based on the conclusions of the research works of Gabaevskaya, Sergeeva 1975, Negaeva 1980, Shamsutdinova 1975, 1983, Makhmudova 2005. In addition, it is necessary to assess the ecological condition of pastures, monitoring and measures for the necessary reclamation, based on the scientific conclusions of the forestry Department, Botanical Scientific Production and a number of other research institutions of the republic.

In our work, we develop technologies for creating pastures with the participation of valuable forage plants, scientifically studied and recommended by scientists of the Republican Scientific Research Institute of Karakul and Desert Ecology, and creating pastures with the participation of shrubby, semi-shrubby and arid plants that hinder the improvement of the ecological state and increase the yield of pastures.

Proper organization of phytomeliorative measures is important for improving the ecological situation on pastures, preventing the process of desertification. Due to the organization and maximum use of artificial agrophytosynthesis, it is possible to increase the yield of pastures by 2-3 times. To do this, it is necessary to study the ecological and biological features of promising species of forage plants that are selected as phytomeliorants. To optimize the ecological state of pastures, work should begin with the organization of agrophytocenoses, based on the conclusions and

recommendations of scientific institutions conducting research in this direction. For example, based on the experience of the Scientific and production Department of Botany of Uzbekistan, the Scientific research Institute of Karakul breeding and Ecology of deserts of Uzbekistan, the forestry Department, it is advisable to use promising nutritious plants recommended by them, such as Isene, teresken, wormwood, astragalus, to increase yields on desert pastures.

Based on our experiments at the Nurlat experimental field of the Research Institute of Soil and Desert Ecology, Izen, camphorosma, teresken, Palin, astragalus, cast iron were selected from promising forage plants as a phytomeliorant to improve the ecological condition and yield of pastures, artificial agrofiocenoses were created with their participation and research work is underway. Based on a comparative assessment of these shrubby, semi-shrubby forage plants, the most suitable for the territory are selected and allocated and artificial agrocenoses are created using them as phytomeliorants to prevent desertification of pastures. The created agrophytocenoses in their viability (15-20 years) and yield exceed natural pastures in pasture - pasture characteristics by 2-3 times, and the yield increased by 3-5 kg/ ha. It is important that the phytomeliorants proposed by us increase the diversity of vegetation on pastures, normalize soil, water and thermal regimes and ensure the stability of the ecosystem as a whole. When performing this urgent task, it is important, based on the conclusions of the research work, guided by agrotechnical rules, to take into account the geographical features of the territory, to create economically significant pastures, to carry out conservation work in the first and second years, to ensure the number of tubers of plants. As a result of the formation of agrophytocenoses, the yield of pastures reaches 3 – 5, their natural state is restored. As a result, desertification processes are prevented. This ensures environmental sustainability.

In addition, the use of pastures without taking into account the phenological phases of plants leads to the loss of the ability of plants to naturally reproduce and re-spread, disruption of the water balance of the soil, causing soil erosion and, ultimately, causing desertification. Carrying out measures to prevent desertification processes in pastures in combination with an increase in pasture yields leads to an increase in the

number and type of plants in the biocenosis. When increasing yields and improving the ecological condition of pastures, it is advisable to carry out phytomeliorative measures, and the use of promising plants in phytomelioration is Cherkez, Chogon, Izen, teresken, keyruk, Palin, etc. it leads to the formation of artificial agrophytocenoses and, ultimately, to an increase in pasture yields by 3-5 times, while ensuring the biological diversity of pastures.

In addition, it is necessary to carry out organizational measures to prevent desertification of pastures. These are the following:

- Compliance with the grazing standards of pasture cattle;
- Grazing of several types of cattle on the same pasture;
- Development and strict compliance with the appropriate rotation scheme for each pasture;
- Constant change of direction during grazing on pastures prevents degradation of plants.
- Use of fences during rotation (alternation) when using pastures;
- Control of plant pruning and root digging;
- Measures to reduce the anthropogenic impact on pastures, etc.

Conclusion. The implementation of the above measures will prevent the process of desertification of pastures, as well as restore their productivity, which will allow the development of animal husbandry and will serve to ensure the food security of our republic. Summing up, we can say that the timely identification of unfavorable situations on pastures, their scientific analysis, compliance with pasture capacity when using pastures, the implementation of phytomeliorative measures based on ensuring the biodiversity of the biocenosis, ensuring the stability of the ecosystem, leading to an increase in pasture yields, contributed to the implementation of food security programs of the republic. important. Ensuring sustainability in the ecosystem ensures the development of environmental sustainability by optimizing the process of desertification.

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